

THE LNGA BA'I BZHI RGYAL 'BIG BSANG OFFERING' IN SGRO RONG BO TIBETAN COMMUNITY, REB GONG, MTSHO SNGON (QINGHAI) PROVINCE, PR CHINA

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ABSTRACT

An A mdo Tibetan ritual locally known as Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal 'Big Bsang Offering' is held on the fifth day of the fifth Chinese lunisolar month in Sgro rong bo (Jiaolongwu) Village, Mdo ba (Duowa) Town, Thun rin (Tongren) City, Rma lho Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. Personal experiences, observations, interviews with local community members, and relevant photographs are provided.

KEYWORDS

Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal, Sgro rong bo, Tibetan ritual, *rgyan mchod*, *bsang* offering, Reb gong, Huangnan

This paper presents Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal, a male-only ritual² held in Sgro rong bo Community in Rma lho (Huangnan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. Officially designated a 'village', Sgro rong bo was a herding community in Mdo ba Town with 212 families and 978 residents in 2023.³ Before 1958, Sgro rong bo included eight *tsho ba* 'subgroups': Sga ru, Sgro tshang, Tsho 'du, Gyu sngogs, Ma ra, Tsho bzhi, Kha rgya, and Lcags so. Locals continued to use the term *tsho ba*. In

¹ I sincerely thank all those who reviewed this paper and made suggestions.

² In 2024, a father might have brought a very young daughter to this ritual, and no one would have been critical. However, there was no memory of females actively participating in the ritual.

³ The 2023 population data here and below were provided in August 2023 by village leader, Lcags thar rgyal (b. 1988).

about 1958, the government created four *ru khag* 'brigades'⁴ - Sgaru, Sgro tshang, Gyu sngogs, and Tsho 'du.

I also discuss changes local people made in 2024 in holding rituals, ritual preparation, and cell phone use and influence.

I began attending the Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal 'Big Bsang⁵ Offering' when I was ten years old in 2001. I eagerly anticipated every festival, ritual, and public activity because I could wear clean clothes, ride horses, and receive candy from others. I begged my father (b. 1964) to let me attend local community activities. Such opportunities were rare because my four siblings and I had to take turns. My elder brother and I received more chances than my three sisters because females could not attend *bsang* offering rituals and *lab tse*⁶ festivals.

I first attended Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal in 2001. Father had announced I would go just as I got home from collecting caterpillar fungi with my elder sisters the night before. I was delighted and asked my mother (b. 1966) to look for my new clothes. She said, "You don't have a new robe, but you can wear your brother's robe, the one you wore last New Year."

I nodded happily. It is usual for children to wear their elder siblings' clothing in families with several children. I regularly wore my elder siblings' clothes since I am the fourth child.

Mother started looking for my favorite leather boots and a Tibetan robe. Father sat on the *hutse* 'heatable bed/eating platform' making *bsang khug* 'food offering bag' with our little hand-powered sewing machine. Father instructed Mother, "Prepare about one and a

⁴ *Ru khag* 'administrative division' was understood as *dadui* in Chinese or *tos*, a Tibetan version of the Chinese term *dui*.

⁵ *Bsang* 'incense', 'incense offerings', 'purification'.

⁶ Locals believe *lab tse* are where mountain deities dwell. *Lab tse* are constructed with wooden poles resembling arrows, sheep wool thread, and stones, suggesting presenting weapons to the mountain deities. Locally, *lab tse* are atop mountains and renewed yearly for locals to receive protection from mountain deities.

half kilograms of butter, a small amount of dry cheese, and *rtsam pa*⁷ 'barley flour' for us to eat tomorrow. Put the butter separately into *za ta*⁸ above the 'barley flour' and cheese."

Mother replied, "I'll do that after preparing clothes for my son. I'm not sure which bag has the Tibetan robes."

As Mother searched, Father told me to collect our livestock in the mountains with my elder sister, Tshe ring skyid (b. 1988). We climbed the mountains in separate directions because our sheep and yaks were grazing on different mountains. Elder Sister soon drove our sheep back. I quickly gathered the yaks and followed as every household noisily herded their livestock into their pens. Elder Sister and I tethered the yaks and fed the young and weak calves corn meal mixed with '*ba cha*'.⁹

Meanwhile, Great Aunt (Mgon po mtsho, 1944-2024) made butter lamps. My family made at least one hundred butter lamps a month and lit them on one of the seven or eight religious days¹⁰ every month. We also lit one or two lamps every night before going to bed. Any family member could light a lamp in front of our shrine shelf, but Great Aunt usually did this in my family. I helped her put ghee into *rkung bu* 'copper butter lamps' and arrange them on a board in front of our shrine shelf.

Mother soon shouted for us to have supper. Father was still sewing *bsang khug* with white cloth and decorating its edges with

⁷ *Rtsam pa* 'roasted barley flour' was a common Tibetan food often mixed with butter, dried cheese, and hot milk tea. Sugar might also have been added. *Rtsam pa* was known by several local names, e.g., local children called it *b+ha b+ha*.

⁸ Two connected cloth pouches for storing *rtsam pa*, cheese, and butter locals used when they went long distances to worship and graze livestock far from their homes.

⁹ Rape meal was commonly fed to livestock (sheep, yaks, and horses).

¹⁰ There are seven or eight auspicious days in a month based on the Chinese lunisolar calendar. Only some months have thirty or thirty-one days. The thirtieth day is the eighth day with religious significance. Certain locals avoided killing livestock and consuming meat during such days. Cabezon (2009:5) writes that "dus bzang days" are considered auspicious.

colorful silk. I hoped the night would pass quickly as I put my clean clothes by my bed and went to bed soon after supper.

Mother woke me around five a.m. with, "Lhu b+ha, get up quickly! Father will take you to Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal. How happy you are today!"

I sat up and said, "Am I late? Has father left?"

Mother said, "Father is saddling our horse. You will leave after breakfast. I prepared everything you need. Hold Father's robe tightly when he takes you on our horse."

I nodded and ate rice porridge, milk, and wild red yams. Father hurriedly returned and said, "Sgrol kho! I saw the rays of our neighbors' flashlights. They are about to leave. Give me *rtsam pa* quickly. We will go with other neighbors. One of them will bring Lhu b+ha. The two of us are too heavy for our horse."

Mother handed Father a bowl of *rtsam pa* and poured tea as he made a ball of *rtsam pa*. After breakfast, he rode our fine horse. I clutched the saddle edge after Mother picked me up and put me behind Father. It was about six-thirty and dark, so Father held a flashlight with the reins.

Representatives from six households went together. About one kilometer from my family's house, Uncle Tshe b+ho'u (b. 1971) joined us, riding a black horse and leading his finest white horse. Uncle said, "A rga rta lo, let Lhu b+ha ride my white horse. You have a big *ta len* 'saddle bags'. Too much weight for your horse."

Father replied, "Your horse must be in today's horse race training. It's not good riding it in the early morning. I'll ask someone else to take him."

Uncle Tshe b+ho'u said, "It's very gentle, so it's not a problem for a little boy to ride it," dismounted and put me on his white horse.

This was my first time to ride a racehorse. I was very excited. I asked Father to let me ride Uncle Tshe b+ho'u's horse and join the horse race. Uncle Tshe b+ho'u and father laughed and said, "Once the horse runs fast, you will be blown away by the wind."

I didn't reply but hoped I would grow up quickly and join horseraces. After we rode for about twenty minutes, we heard birds

flying and chirping. Father no longer held the flashlight as it became lighter around us.

When we neared our destination, we could see the *bsang khri* where the Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal ritual was held annually. Father kicked his horse to speed up and said, "We should go faster. Others have probably arrived and are making *rgyan mchod*."¹¹

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PHOTOGRAPHS

FIG 1. Second Brigade Sga ru residents waited for this *rgyan mchod* to be offered on the fifth day of the fifth Chinese lunisolar month (2020, Lhun 'grub). *Rgyan mchod* was a term for butter figures shaped like *dkar gtor* 'sculptured dough offering'. The *dkar gtor*'s two wings resembled garuda wings. A *dkar gtor* had a sharp-pointed top, a round bulbous middle, and a wide round bottom. The sharp top indicated hope for a sharp mind, the rounded middle was hope for wealth, and the round, wide bottom was hope for solid power. A khu dpon Tshe ring rnam rgyal (b. 1966), a lay tantrik practitioner, came to my home to chant *Sgrol ma'i rlung rta*¹² in 2019. I asked what objects should be prepared to make a *dkar gtor* when Father and I were making *dkar gtor* for *bsang* offerings. He explained, "*Dkar* means "white" and refers to *dkar gsum*, 'the three main foods with no connection to meat (milk, yogurt, and butter)'. You also need *ngar gsum*, 'the three main sweets' (white sugar, honey, and brown sugar) used to make a good *dkar gtor*."

¹¹ Figures of sacramental cakes made with butter.

¹² *Sgrol ma'i rlung rta* 'The Wind Horse of the Liberating Goddess' is a scripture often associated with Sgrol ma/Tara, who embodies compassion and swift assistance.

FIG 2. The Sgro rong bo *bsang khri* 'offering altar'¹³ where villagers often burnt *bsang* just after offering *bsang* during Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal in Sgro rong bo Village on the fifth day of the fifth Chinese

¹³ *Bsang khri*: *Bsang* 'incense offering' 'purification'. *Khri* 'stupa base'. *Bsang khri* refers to the stupa or where villagers often offer *bsang*.

lunisolar month (2021, Bo kho). Locals believed Sgro rong bo'i bsang khri was built during the time of the Third Skyabs mgon¹⁴ incarnation. The Third's saddles, saddle blankets, and bridles were placed at the stupa center, which was believed to provide protection and help from A myes gur.¹⁵ For example, locals circumambulated the *bsang khri* to cure heart disease.

'Dzam gling spyi bsang had several interpretations. A khu dpon tshe ring rnam rgyal explained via WeChat:

This practice didn't start in recent years. I recall participating in 'Dzam gling spyi bsang as a child, but I need clarification on its origins. According to elders, every time 'Dzam gling ge sar rgyal po (King Gesar of 'Dzam gling) was victorious in battle, a grand *bsang* offering was held to celebrate. Over time, it became a tradition. The date for 'Dzam gling spyi bsang is not standardized. It is observed on the fifteenth day of the fifth Tibetan lunisolar¹⁶ month in the Lha sa vicinity, the eleventh day of the second Chinese lunisolar month in farming regions around Thun rin (Tongren) City, and the fifth day of the fifth Chinese lunisolar month in herding areas such as Sgro rong bo."

¹⁴ A general name for eight incarnations of Shar skyabs mgon skal ldan rgya mthso: Yab rje bla ma shar skyabs mgon skal ldan rgya mthso (1607-1677), Ngag dbang 'phrin las rgya mtsho (1678-1714), Dge 'dun 'phrin las rab rgyas (1740-1794), Blo bzang chos grags rgya mtsho (1794-1843), Blo bzang 'phrin las rgya mtsho (1843-1844), Blo bzang bstan pa'i rgya mtsho (1844-1858), Blo bzang 'phrin las lung rtogs rgya mtsho (1916-1978), and Bstan 'dzin 'jigs med skal ldan dpal bzang (b. 1979). See *Dung dkar tshig mdzod chen mo* (2002:2329) for more.

¹⁵ A myes gur is a form of Mahakala originally from Sa skya Monastery in Sa skya Town, Sa skya County, about 127 kilometers west of Gzhis ka rtse (Shigatse City), the Tibet Autonomous Region. The deity was invited to Rong bo Monastery, and a temple was built. Rtse khog villagers and certain farming areas in Reb gong worshipped it. See *Mdo smad lo rgyus chen mo* (2009:410) for more.

¹⁶ This calendar is based on the Tibetan Lunisolar Calendar used in the Lha sa City area. When Sgro rong bo locals employed the term Bod rtis 'Tibetan lunisolar calendar', they referred to the Chinese lunisolar calendar. However, this refers more widely to the former calendar.

Another account explained that when Padmasambhava came to Tibet and established Bsam yas gtsug lag khang 'Bsam yas Monastery,' a grand *bsang* offering was held to commemorate the monastery's founding. Later, it came to be known as 'Dzam gling spyi bsang.'¹⁷

Locals believed 'Dzam gling spyi bsang' was held in many Tibetan areas. *Spyi bsang* referred to a collective *bsang* offering, commonly held at the beginning of summer, to worship mountain deities and the hope for healthy livestock and bountiful harvests in farming areas. The location where the *bsang* offering was made – the *bsang khri* - ranged from a small flat stone area to a larger space where a hundred sacks of barley might have been offered. Each family's house in Sgro rong bo had a *bsang khri* behind it. When moving among different pastures for grazing, a father's first task was to create a *bsang khri* and offer *bsang* to the mountain deities to ward off potential harm such as illness, livestock theft, and storm disasters in the new pasture.

¹⁷ 'Dzam gling suggests 'universe' and 'King 'Dzam gling'.

FIG 3. *Bon rgya* attended to chant scriptures associated with 'Jigs byed 'Bhairava' transmitted by Shar skyabs mgon skal ldan rgya mtsho. (Rtse khog County Town, 16 October 2022, Skal bzang rgya mtsho). *Bon rgya* (CT; LT: *ban rgya*)¹⁸ traditionally referred to monks, but locals in my home area used this term to describe people who performed rituals in Sgro rong bo. Local families easily enlisted the help of *bon rgya* members to conduct rituals as instructed by a *bla ma* or a *rtsis ba* 'diviner'. *Bon rgya* were originally selected from Sgro rong bo for several reasons. First, geographical isolation from our county town and Rong bo Monastery¹⁹ meant two days for our ancestors to reach Rong bo Monastery and invite monks to their homes to chant and hold rituals. After reaching the monastery, finding monks willing to come to Mdo ba was challenging due to the long distance and inconvenient transportation. As a solution, our ancestors chose locals who could read Tibetan, learn simple rituals and scripture chants, and perform what they had been taught. This became a tradition and was passed down to subsequent generations. Dating this system is ongoing. However, according to information shared by A khu dpon tshe ring rnam rgyal in 2022, the *bon rgya* tradition has a history of five generations. As of 2023, twenty *bon*

¹⁸ CT=colloquial Tibetan; LT=Literary Tibetan. It should also be noted that a farming village in Reb gong and a large herding community in Rtse khog have the same name - Bon rgya.

¹⁹ Rong bo Monastery (Rong bo bde chen chos 'khor gling) is a Dge lugs monastery in Thun rin City, Rma lho Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture. Nian and Bai (1993:153) attributed the monastery's founding to Bsam gtan rin chen (Sanmudan Renqi), the eldest son of Mdo sde 'bum (Dodé Bum). Bsam gtan rin chen later became the head of Rong bo Monastery. The monastery's spiritual lineage is rooted in the teachings of Chos rje don grub rin chen (Chöjé Döndrup Rinchen, 1290-1364), who taught Tsong kha ba. Rong bo bsam gtan rin chen (Rongwo Samten Rinchen), Chos rje don grub rin chen's disciple, played a significant role in the monastery's history. Furthermore, Shar skyabs mgon skal ldan rgya mthso (1607-1677) is acknowledged as the first reincarnation of Bsam gtan rin chen and is known for his service as the abbot of Rong bo bde chen chos 'khor gling.

rgya members chanted various scriptures and performed more complex rituals, e.g., Bskang ba, Rta mgrin bzlog pa, and G.yang 'bod.

FIG 4. In 2021, Sgro rong bo had twenty *bon rgya*.

Names	Year of Birth
Sko lo	1943
Aja' dbyangs dphal ldan	1954
Tshe go	1955
Mgo rgya	1958
Rtam kho	1965
Rta mgrin dbang rgyal	1965
Tshe lug	1966
Rta mgrin tshe ring	1967
Rdo rje	1970
Mchod rtan	1972
Sgrol dkar skyabs	1973
Rta b+he	1975
Ka me	1977
Rta ma	1978
Rta lo	1981
Skal bzang rgya mtsho	1983

Lcags thar rgyal	1983
Tshe ring rnam rgyal	1983
Sha bo	1993
Rdo rje tshe ring	2001

FIG 5. *Bon rgya* chanted scriptures during Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal when villagers offered *bsang*. They sat by the *bsang khri* and chanted together. Scriptures' names and descriptions:

Scripture names	Details
Skyabs 'gro sems bskyed 'The Generation of Mind from Taking Refuge' is a four-line verse from the short text proper, known as <i>Taking Refuge</i> .	Locals say, " <i>Chos kyi sngon ma skyabs 'gro, zas kyi sngon ma mchod kha</i> 'Chant Skyabs 'gro before every chanting, offer deities every time before you eat.'" Skyabs 'gro should be chanted at the start of every chanting to take refuge in the Three Jewels ²⁰ while imagining and expecting enlightenment for all beings suffering from heat, cold, and hunger. Enlightenment for other beings is <i>sems bskyed</i> 'mind generation'.
Bla ma'i gsol 'debs 'Pray for <i>Bla ma</i> '	<i>Bla ma</i> refers to the <i>bla ma</i> who historically have religious connections with locals who believe in the same sect, and mostly live in the monastery where villagers worship often. Locals also say and believe, " <i>Gzhan gyi bla ma rtsi tog yin, rang gi bla ma me tog yin</i> 'See other <i>bla ma</i> of different places as an abundance of weeds, see your own <i>bla ma</i> as flowers among the weeds.'" One's personal <i>bla ma</i> should be worshiped first.

²⁰ The Buddha, dharma, and sangha are Buddhism's three jewels. Buddha refers to the first Buddha and the awakening and enlightenment Buddhists seek. The Dharma is Buddhism's teachings. The sangha is a community of understanding and love that helps guide toward enlightenment, accessed 18 November 2024.

	<i>Bla ma</i> also refers to teachers, explaining why locals believe teachers should be always respected.
Yi dam skad gcig drung skyed 'Tutelary Deity Skad gcig drung skyed '	One <i>bon rgya</i> told me when <i>bon rgya</i> start chanting, they should concentrate on the tutelary deity possessing them while beseeching mountain deities to protect the villagers from harms and difficulties.
Chos skyong gi bsang 'Bsang for Dharma Protectors' ²¹	<i>Bsang</i> is offered to <i>bla ma</i> , <i>yi dam</i> , <i>chos skyong</i> , and <i>gzhi bdag</i> in this order. <i>Gzhi bdag</i> refers to local deities, potent spirits associated with the region. Locals believed that they need good luck to complete whatever they do, and only local deities can help bring good luck. For example, locals collected caterpillar fungi from the beginning of the fourth to the middle of the fifth lunar months. Before collecting caterpillar fungi, they offered <i>bsang</i> to the local deities to ask for help to collect as many caterpillar fungi as possible. Sgro rong bo, where I was born and raised, was home to five primary <i>gzhi bdag</i> 'local deities': A myes skyer lung, A myes gyag smying, A myes rdza rgan, A myes shug rgan, and A myes ri rgan.
Rlung rta'i <i>bsang</i> 'Bsang of Wind Horses'	
Gzhi bdag gi bsang 'Bsang for Mountain Deities'	
Bsngo ba dang smon lam 'Dedication and Aspiration'	

²¹ It is a generic term referring to any verse of supplication to mountain deities, not the name of a particular ritual text. The same case is true for the next three entries in the table.

HE LNGA BA'I BZHI RGYAL RITUAL

PREPARATION

The day before the Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal festival, Sgro rong bo village elders met at a local home near the *bsang khri*. They discussed what villagers should bring to the festival, e.g., butter, milk, cash, kettles, water containers, pots, sacks of dry yak dung for fuel, and juniper, and the amount to collect from each brigade or family. Other issues included which brigade should make *bsang khug*²² (and of what color), how many *bsang khug* they should make, and who should make *rgyan mchod* in each brigade because only a few men were skilled at making flowers, goats, conch shells, and gems out of butter.

After discussion and assigning work to the four brigades, each brigade leader returned to their brigade and assigned responsibilities. For example, each family head needed to bring one and a half kilograms of butter, two bottles of milk, and two *rgya ma* of *rtsam pa*.

Before 2012, brigade leaders rode monocycles to inform villagers what they needed to do, bring, and prepare for *rgyan mchod*. After WeChat became widely popular, each brigade formed a WeChat group, and village leaders sent directions via WeChat.

We made *rgyan mchod* on the festival day when I was a child and offered it as part of *bsang*. Consequently, we only needed to prepare a little before the festival day. Later, making *rgyan mchod* was competitive between brigades, and elders evaluated which brigade's *rgyan mchod* was the best size, appearance, and completeness. Consequently, every family head gathered at a home where everyone could meet conveniently and make *rgyan mchod*. Every family was required to give *rus cha*²³ the day before Lnga ba'i

²² *Bsang khug* refers to self-made cloth bags for *bsang rtsi* men carried when offering *bsang*.

²³ *Rus cha* is a local term for collecting food, equipment, and cash to do

bzhi rgyal. An absent family head was required to give '*grig*,²⁴ so few missed the preparation meeting.

Moreover, on the preparation day, men skilled in creating butter figures made a *rgyan mchod* model by binding three pieces of wood together in the shape of a bird with a height of approximately 1.6 meters. The butter contributions from each household were combined and mixed until it was pliable enough to make figures. Next, skilled men made *rgyan mchod* with well-mixed butter while other men made *rstam pa* dough for *dkar stor*. Only men made *rgyan mchod*.²⁵

While making the *rgyan mchod*²⁶ model, *rtsam pa* dough, and *bsang rtsi*,²⁷ flowers, conch shells, and livestock figures were not made. Those were relatively easy tasks, so locals made them on the festival day when locals arrived at the *bsang khri*. Instead, villagers prepared around ten sacks of dried yak dung, *su ru* 'brushwood', and juniper for offerings the next day. They disbanded at around nine p.m. and returned home.

THE LNGA BA'I BZHI RGYAL FESTIVAL DAY

Take orning of Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal, villagers, especially men, got up early, offered a small amount of *bsang* behind their houses, and prepared what they would take to the festival. *Bsang rtsi* consisted of mostly *sher rtsig* 'roasted barley' with butter, brown sugar, *bsang*

something, e.g., a collective ritual activity with collected money and food. *Rus cha* was written as *rug khral* 'collecting tax' in textbooks.

²⁴ '*Grig* was a local term indicating punishment for being absent from meetings and rituals.

²⁵ Men did not share a bed with women before attending important competitions such as horse races to avoid bad luck to the man. Additionally, men avoided having sex during a woman's menstrual period because it was thought to weaken a man's fortune. A husband also avoided being near his wife when she gave birth.

²⁶ *Rgyan* 'decoration', *mchod* 'offer', refers to the detailed work of making butter flowers, conch shells, and livestock figures.

²⁷ Roasted barley to offer mountain deities.

rdzas ril bu 'local monastery made grain pills', raisins, red jujubes, fresh fruit, crystal sugar, milk, and yogurt. *Dkar zas* 'vegetarian food' might have been offered to mountain deities who were *dkar phyogs* 'peaceful deities'.²⁸ *Dkar zas* was only offered to mountain deities during the Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal day.

After *bsang rtsi* preparations, men wore new Tibetan robes to attend the festival. Before 2002, there were only three motorcycles in Sgro rong bo. Those without motorcycles rode horses to the festival. Later, more villagers bought motorcycles, trucks, and small cars. No one rode horses to festivals in 2003.

Villagers arrived at the *bsang khri* site at around nine a.m. Locals recognized *bsang* as offerings to mountain deities. Some villagers offered sacks of barley, tea bricks, and butter to mountain deities, especially when there was illness and traffic accidents, and when attending large competitions, horsing races, and celebrating special days such as Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal. Villagers also referred to *bsang* as *bsang mchod* 'bsang offering' and believed that the more offerings they made, the more protection mountain deities would bestow.

During Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal, villagers offered the largest *bsang* offering they made annually. Every man from each household joined. If a man could not join, their family entrusted *bsang rtsi* and other offerings to a relative or friend, so every household was included in offerings.

Before offering the big *bsang* on the festival day, young men cleaned the *bsang khri*. They removed ash, put dry brushwood in a circle, spread dry yak dung and juniper branches over the brushwood, and flattened it. Offerings steadily increased. The flames intensified after setting fire to the brushwood, and everyone began chanting a *bsang* scripture loudly. At this time, each brigade's *rgyan mchod* was offered. Young men from each brigade placed the *rgyan mchod* on the fire in turn. The four *rgyan mchod*

²⁸ Cabezón (2009) classified mountain deities as *dkar phyogs* and *nag phyogs* 'wrathful deities'.

were set on the fire in the four directions. Villagers put *gos* 'silk cloth' around the four *rgyan mchod* after it was set on fire. Lastly, each man held up their *bsang khug* and offerings to offer their own *bsang*. Offering procedures were as below:

- 1 Offer *dkar zas* food, garment silk, tea bricks, and *kha btags*.
- 2 Offer tea, milk, yogurt, liquor, and drinks.
- 3 Blow conch shells.
- 4 Set off fireworks.
- 5 Scatter paper *rlung rta*.
- 6 Pour *chub*.²⁹
- 7 Circumambulate the *bsang khri* and shout praises of deities.
- 8 *Bon rgya* and *bsang* chanting and scriptures

HORSERACE PREPARATION

The festival ended at around two p.m. after lunch at the *ba kha*.³⁰ Locals brought one or two bottles of milk from each household and made a big pot of milk tea with black brick tea. Every man brought his *za ta* with *rstam pa*, cheese, butter, and one or two bowls. Villagers drank milk tea and ate *rtsam pa*. However, after about 2015, fewer people brought *za ta* and ate *rtsam pa*. Instead, they mainly ate fried noodles, eggs, rice, and vegetables and drank Pepsi and Coca-Cola. Various snacks were brought from shops and restaurants in Mdo ba Town or shops near Gad dmar Primary School, located about ten kilometers from Mdo ba Town to the west.

Before 2010, locals rode horses to Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal. Once the *bsang* offering was complete and after lunch, villagers rode to a wide grassland known as Gad dmar thang, one kilometer from the *bsang khri*. Horses that would participate in the horserace on the seventeenth day of the fifth Chinese lunisolar month rehearsed on

²⁹ Purified water.

³⁰ *Ba kha* 'three-stone hearth', *ba ma* 'pot set atop the stones', *ba kha* 'area around the hearth'. During Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal, each brigade had a *ba kha* where villagers had lunch in four groups after finishing the *bsang* offering.

this day. The horse owners took their horses to the starting line while other men went to a higher location to watch and enjoy the horserace.

CONCLUSION

Amid changing social dynamics, Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal in 2023 was an intricate dance between tradition and modernity. Once a large, important part of community life, it has become simpler because more young people can read and chant scriptures for the families who previously asked their respected *bla ma* or tantric practitioner to chant based on annual divination results. Years ago, only monks chanted scriptures for families. Holding rituals and chanting scriptures became more expensive, so many families only invited monks to chant scriptures if it was too complex for local young people. However, some wealthier families continued inviting monks to chant scriptures, believing the results were better.

Cell phones and cars have added new aspects to this situation. Even though young people love these new things, they also want to or are being asked to maintain their traditions. Local rituals are critical to maintaining traditions, and youth familiar with using technology are challenged to maintain local rituals enthusiastically.

The difficult truth is that many rituals and traditions may disappear. With communal activities becoming less frequent and the appeal of a quickly changing world driven by new technology like AI, finding time to hold rituals becomes more challenging. There is a real threat to continuing these cultural practices. The younger generation is at a crossroads between the excitement of a new, fast-paced society and the responsibility to protect traditions and knowledge from their ancestors.

In navigating this delicate balance, will the younger generation see how important it is to keep local culture alive? While the modern world offers many conveniences and new things, will connecting tradition and evolution be seen as important? Finding new and creative ways to bring rituals into today's world might be

encouraged by using digital platforms or adjusting them to fit changing society. For example, the main idea of the annual Gter sgrub ritual was for locals to understand and appreciate the importance of the earth and embrace thanksgiving as they participated for the sake of peace with the *sa bdag* 'landlord' and thus achieve more benefits from the earth.

Building a sense of community and shared responsibility is crucial. Permanent settlements and fewer social interactions make this challenging. Encouraging ritual participation strengthens a sense of community.

In essence, Lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal represents global changes with old traditions struggling against the forces of modernization. The younger generation must find new ways to blend tradition with the future, not just to cherish and protect their culture. A culture's true strength lies in this delicate balance – the ability to change without forgetting its roots. As we stand between tradition and progress, the challenge is to retain knowledge of the past while moving forward into an unknown future, armed with the wisdom of our ancestors and the courage to embrace change.

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Zlog pa grub chen las kyi rdo rje ལྷོག་པ་གུབ་ཆེན་ལས་ཀྱི་རྩོམ་པ་འཇམ་དཔལ་ལྷན་པ་གྲགས་པོ། nd. *Gdugs dkar mchog grub ma bzhugs so གདུགས་དཀར་མཚོག་གུབ་མ་བཞུགས་སོ།* [The White Parasol].

TIBETAN TERMS

'ba' cha འབའ་ཇ།

'bo ra འཛོ་ར།

'dge 'dun chos 'phel slob'bring དགོ་འདུན་ཚོས་འཕེལ་སློབ་འབྲིང་།

'dzam gling འཛམ་གླིང་།

'dzam gling ge sar rgyal po འཛམ་གླིང་གོ་སར་རྒྱལ་པོ།

'dzam gling spyi bsang འཛམ་གླིང་སྤྱི་བསང་།

'grig འགྲིག་

'jigs byed འཇིགས་བྱེད།

a khu dpon ཨ་ཁུ་དཔོན།

a khu dpon tshe ring rnam rgyal ཨ་ཁུ་དཔོན་ཚེ་རིང་རྣམ་རྒྱལ།

a myes gur ཨ་མྱེས་གུར།

a myes gyag smying ཨ་མྱེས་གཡག་སྦྱིང་།

a myes rdza rgan ཨ་མྱེས་རྩ་རྒྱན།

a myes ri rgan ཨ་མྱེས་རི་རྒྱན།

a myes shug rgan ཨ་མྱེས་ཤུག་རྒྱན།

a myes skyer lung ཨ་མྱེས་སྦྱེར་ལུང་།

a rga rta lo ཨ་རྒྱ་རྟ་ལོ།

aja' dbyangs dphal ldan འཇམ་དབྱངས་དཔལ་ལྷན།

b+ha b+ha བ་ཧ་བ་ཧ།

ba kha བ་ཀ།

ba ma བ་མ།

bad+ma rig 'dzin བད་མ་རིག་འདེན།

bon rgya བོན་རྒྱ།

bka' 'gyur བཀའ་འགྲུས།

bla ma ལྷ་མ།

bla ma'i gsol 'debs ལྷ་མའི་གསོལ་འདེབས།

blo bzang 'phrin las lung rtogs rgya mtsho ལྷོ་བཟང་འཕྲིན་ལས་ལུང་རྟོགས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

blo bzang 'phrin las rgya mtsho ལྷོ་བཟང་འཕྲིན་ལས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

blo bzang bstan pa'i rgya mtsho ལྷོ་བཟང་བསྟན་པའི་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

blo bzang chos grags rgya mtsho ལྷོ་བཟང་ཚོས་གཤམ་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

bod rtsis བོད་རྗེས།

bsam gtan rin chen, sanmudan renqi བསམ་གཏན་རིན་ཆེན།

bsam yas gtsug lag khang བསམ་ཡས་གཙུག་ལག་ཁང།

bsang བསང།

bsang khri བསང་ཁྲི།

bsang khug བསང་ཁུག།

bsang rdzas ril bu བསང་རྩས་རིལ་བུ།

bsang rtsi བསང་རྗེ།

bskang ba བསྐང་བ།

bsngo ba dang smon lam བསོ་བ་དང་སྟོན་ལམ།

bstan 'dzin 'jigs med skal ldan dpal bzang བསྟན་འདེན་འཇིགས་མེད་སྐལ་ལྷན་དཔལ་བཟང།

bstod བསྟོད།

bstod smon phyogs bsgrigs བསྟོད་སྟོན་ཕྱོགས་བསྐྱེགས།

bzhi ba'i smyung gnas བཞི་བའི་སྦྱང་གནས།

cho ga ཚོ་ག།

chos kyi sngon ma skyabs 'gro, zas kyi sngon ma mchod kha

ཚོས་ཀྱི་ཚོན་མ་སྐབས་འགྲོ། བས་ཀྱི་ཚོན་མ་མཚོད་ལ།

chos rje don grub rin chen, Chöjé Döndrup Rinchen ཚོས་རྗེ་དོན་གྲུབ་རིན་ཆེན།

chos skyong ཚོས་སྦྱང།

chos skyong gi bsang ཚོས་སྦྱང་གི་བསང།

chub ཚུབ།

g.yang 'bod གཡལ་འབོད།

dge 'dun 'phrin las rab rgyas དགོ་འདུན་འཕྲིན་ལས་རབ་རྒྱས།

dge 'dun chos 'phel དགོ་འདུན་ཚོས་འཕེལ།

dge lugs དགེ་ལུགས།
dgu chu དགུ་ཅུ།
dkar དཀར།
dkar gsum དཀར་གསུམ།
dkar gtor དཀར་གཏོར།
dkar phyogs དཀར་ཕྱོགས།
dkar zas དཀར་ཟས།
dkon mchog gsum དཀོན་མཚོག་གསུམ།
dpon དཔོན།
dung dkar blo bzang 'phrin las ཏུང་དཀར་ལྷོ་བཟང་འཕྲིན་ལས།
dung dkar tshig mdzod chen mo ཏུང་དཀར་ཚིག་མཛོད་ཆེན་མོ།
dus bzang ཏུས་བཟང་།
dus chen ཏུས་ཆེན།
g.yang 'bod གཡང་འབོད།
gad dmar གད་དམར།
gad dmar thang གད་དམར་ཐང་།
gter གཏེར།
gter sgrub གཏེར་སྐྱབ།
gyu rngog གཡུ་རྫོག།
gzhi bdag གཞི་བདག།
gzhi bdag gi bsang གཞི་བདག་གི་བསང་།
gzhis ka rtse གཞིས་ཀ་རུཙ།
gzhan gyi bla ma rts'i tog yin, rang gi bla ma me tog yin
གཞན་གྱི་བླ་མ་རྗེ་ཏོག་ཡིན། རང་གི་བླ་མ་མེ་ཏོག་ཡིན།
hor gtsang 'jigs med ཧོར་གཙང་འཇིགས་མེད།
ka me ཀ་མེ།
kha btags ཀ་བཏགས།
kha rgya ཀ་རྒྱ།
khri srong lde btsan ཁྲི་སྲོང་ལྗེ་བཙན།
lab tse ལམ་ཙེ།
lcags so ལུགས་སོ།
lcags thar rgyal ལུགས་ཐར་རྒྱལ།
lha sa ལྷ་ས།
lhu b+ha ལུ་བླ།
lnga ba'i bzhi rgyal ལྷ་བའི་བཞི་རྒྱལ།

ma ra མ་ར།
mchod rtan མཚོད་རྟེན།
mdo མདོ།
mdo ba མདོ་བ།
mdo gdugs sgrol gsum མདོ་གདུགས་སྐོལ་གསུམ།
mdo sde 'bum, Dodé Bum མདོ་སྡེ་འབུམ།
mdo smad lo rgyus chen mo མདོ་སྦྱང་ལོ་རྒྱལ་ཚེན་མོ།
mgo rgya མགོ་རྒྱ།
mgon po mtsho མགོན་པོ་མཚོ།
mngar gsum མངར་གསུམ།
mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྐོལ།
nag phyogs ནག་ཕྱོགས།
ngag dbang 'phrin las rgya mtsho ངག་དབང་འཕྲིན་ལས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།
rdo rje རོ་རྗེ།
rdo rje tshe ring རོ་རྗེ་ཚེ་རིང།
reb gong རེབ་གོང།
rgya 'du རྒྱ་འདུ།
rgya ma རྒྱ་མ།
rgyan mchod རྒྱན་མཚོད།
rim gro རིམ་གྲོ།
rlung rta'i bsang རླང་རྟའི་བསང།
rma lho རྩ་ལྟོ།
rong bo རོང་བོ།
rong bo bde chen chos 'khor gling རོང་བོ་བདེ་ཚེན་ཚས་འཁོར་གླིང།
rta mgrin bzlog pa རྟ་མགིན་བཟོག་པ།
rta mgrin dbang rgyal རྟ་མགིན་དབང་རྒྱལ།
rta mgrin tshe brtan རྟ་མགིན་ཚེ་བརྟན།
rta mgrin tshe ring རྟ་མགིན་ཚེ་རིང།
rta b+he རྟ་ཞེ།
rta lo རྟ་ལོ།
rta ma རྟ་མ་མ།
rtam kho རྟ་མ་ཁོ།
rtsam pa རྟ་མ་པ།
rtse khog རྟེ་ཁོག།
rtsis ba རྟེས་བ།

rug རུག

ru khag རུ་ཁག

rug khral རུག་ཁྲལ།

rug khya རུག་ཁྱལ།

rus cha རུས་ཇ།

sa skya ས་སྐྱལ།

sa gter ས་གཏེར།

sa bdag ས་བདག

Samten G Karmay, mkhar rme'u bsam gtan མཁའ་རྩེ་བསམ་གཏུན།

sems bskyed སེམས་བསྐྱེད།

sga ru སྐ་རུ།

sgro rong bo སྐོར་རོང་བོ།

sgro rong bo'i bsang khri སྐོར་རོང་བོའི་བསང་ཁྲི།

sgro tshang སྐོར་ཚང།

sgrol dkar སྐོལ་དཀར།

sgrol dkar skyabs སྐོལ་དཀར་སྐྱབས།

sgrol kho སྐོལ་ཁོ།

sgrol ma, Tara སྐོལ་མ།

sgrol ma mtsho སྐོལ་མ་མཚོ།

sgrol ma'i rlung rta སྐོལ་མའི་རླུང་རྟ།

sha bo ཤ་བོ།

shar skyabs mgon skal ldan rgya mthso ཤར་སྐྱབས་མགོན་སྐལ་ལྷན་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

sher rtsig ཤེར་རྩིག

shu rgan lab tse ཤུག་གན་ལབ་ཙེ།

shug rgan zho 'thung ཤུག་གན་ཞོ་འཇུང།

skal bzang rgya mtsho སྐལ་བཟང་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

sko lo སྐོ་ལོ།

rkung bu རུང་བུ།

skyabs 'gro སྐྱབས་འགོ།

skyabs 'gro sems bskyed སྐྱབས་འགོ་སེམས་བསྐྱེད།

skyabs mgon སྐྱབས་མགོན།

stong mchod སྟོང་མཚོད།

su ru སུ་རུ།

ta len ཏ་ལེན།

thun rin ཐུན་རིན།

tos ཏོས།

tshe go ཚེ་གོ།

tshe lug ཚེ་ལུག།

tshe ring skyid ཚེ་རིང་སྐྱིད།

tsho 'du ཚོ་འདུ།

tsho ba ཚོ་བ།

tsho bzhi ཚོ་བཞི།

tsong kha ba ཚོང་ཁ་བ།

yab rje bla ma shar skyabs mgon skal ldan rgya mtsho

ཡབ་རྗེ་བླ་མ་ཤར་སྐལ་མགོན་ལྷན་ཀླུ་མཚོ།

yi dam skad gcig drung skyed ཡི་དམ་སྐད་གཅིག་རྩུང་སྐྱེད།

yo lag ཡོ་ལག།

za ta ཟ་ཏ།

CHINESE TERMS

Bai 白

Bai Gengdeng 白更登

dadui 大队

dui 队

Duowa 多哇

Gashenzi 瓜什则

Huangnan 黄南

jin 斤

Lanzhou 兰州

Nian Zhihai 年治海

Qinghai 青海

Qinghai zangchuan fojiao siyuan mingjian 青海藏传佛教寺院明鉴

Sangjie Zhaxi 桑杰扎西

Sumudan Renqin 叁木丹仁青

Tongren 同仁

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